

Two- and Three-Dimensional Osteometric Variability of the Foramen Magnum in Modern Humans

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Supplementary material – S1 – Introduction

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Supplementary material – S1.1

Permission letter 1 – Berliner Gesellschaft für Anthropologie, Ethnologie und
Urgeschichte (for the Rudolf-Virchow-Collection)

Supplementary Material, Introduction – S1.3

Schematic Illustration of the Foramen Magnum and the Structures Running Through It

Anterior FM matrix (A)

- 1 - Anterior atlantooccipital membrane
- 2 - Odontoid process (dens) of axis
- 3 - Apical odontoid ligament of dens
- 4 - Odontoid or alar ligament*
- 5 - Transverse occipital ligaments
- 6 - Accessory atlantoaxial(-occipital) ligaments L/R
- 7 - Superior longitudinal band of cruciform ligament of atlas (curs superius)
- 8 - Tectorial membrane of atlanto-axial joint

Posterior FM matrix (B)

- 9 - Posterior internal vertebral venous plexus
 - 10 - Extradural space
 - 11 - Dura mater
 - 12 - Subdural space
 - 13 - Arachnoid mater
 - 14 - Subarachnoid space with cerebrospinal fluid
 - 15 - Pia mater
 - 16 - White matter of spinal cord
 - 17 - Grey matter of spinal cord
 - 18 - Central canal of spinal cord
 - 19 - Vertebral artery*
 - 20 - Anterior spinal artery
 - 21 - Spinal root of accessory nerve*
 - 22 - Posterior vertebral artery*
 - 23 - Tonsil of cerebellum*
 - 24 - Posterior atlantooccipital membrane
- } Meninges (11-15)
} Medulla oblongata (16-18)

Fig. S1.3: Schematic overview of the structures passing through the foramen magnum. Anterior is facing upwards. Not to scale. * = bilateral occurring structures. Designed by the author, modified after Inderbir (2012), Matsushima (2015), Tubbs et al. (2010b), and Tubbs et al. (2004). Created with Procreate® (version 4.3.9) using the Apple iPad® (6th generation, version 15.1) and Apple Pencil®.

Supplementary Material, Introduction – S1.4 and S1.5

Fig. S1.4a (left) and S1.4b (right): Indicated by the white arrows are examples of foramen magnum tubercles. Ectocranial view. Anterior is up. Left: Basion tubercle (3.37 mm) in a German individual (RV 901, included in the analysis of the present study). Right: Opisthion tubercle (4.74 mm) in an individual from Sri Lanka (RV 45, not included in the present analysis).

Tab. S1.5: Radiocarbon dates of the six RVS Kohaito skulls. Calibration after quickcal2007 ver.1.5 (table adapted (not modified) from (Wenig and Vogt, 2017)).

Probe ID	RVS-ID	BP	BP Error	calAD	Laboratory ID
Virchow 03/12-1	RV 1065	934	± 45	1096 ± 52	Erl-17301
Virchow 03/12-2	RV 1283	530	± 46	1375 ± 47	Erl-17302
Virchow 03/12-3	RV 1284	69	± 49	1240 ± 29	Erl-17303
Virchow 03/12-4	RV 1292	946	± 50	1091 ± 54	Erl-17304
Virchow 03/12-5	RV 1296	912	± 50	1112 ± 60	Erl-17305
Virchow 03/12-6	RV 1306	642	± 60	1336 ± 45	Erl-17306

RVS-ID = Rudolf-Virchow-Collection inventory number, BP = before present, calAD = calibrated radiocarbon age. RV 1292 is not included in the analyses of this study.